

Remote Follow-up Application for Dengue Patients: Innovation in Symptom Management and Clinical Monitoring

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Abstract— Dengue, a disease transmitted by the *Aedes aegypti* mosquito, affects millions of people annually, posing challenges in patient care and clinical follow-up, especially in areas with limited medical infrastructure. This work presents the development of a remote follow-up application for patients with confirmed or suspected dengue, allowing users to record their symptoms so that the system can automatically classify the severity of each case. Remote follow-up enables healthcare professionals to track symptom progression, identify early warning signs, and adjust treatment as needed, reducing unnecessary travel to healthcare facilities. The methodology included Design Thinking to understand user needs. This tool is expected to improve patient experience and optimize resource usage during periods of high dengue incidence, providing personalized and easily accessible follow-up.

Keywords — dengue, remote follow-up, mobile application, diagnosis, symptom classification

I. INTRODUCTION

Dengue is an arbovirus transmitted by the *Aedes aegypti* mosquito, affecting approximately 390 million people per year, with only 96 million presenting clinical symptoms, according to the World Health Organization (WHO) [1]. As a disease prevalent in tropical and subtropical regions, it proliferates mostly in countries with favorable climate conditions. In Brazil it affects around 1 million people annually, based on data from the Ministry of Health's historical series of probable cases [2].

Symptoms vary from mild to severe, or even asymptomatic [3]. The most common symptoms include high fever, intense muscle and joint pain, headache, retro-orbital pain, red skin rashes, and extreme fatigue [4]. In severe cases, patients may present bleeding, low blood pressure, shock, and even death, requiring urgent hospitalization [5]. These symptoms often resemble other viral infections such as Chikungunya and Zika, which makes dengue diagnosis more complex and its treatment more specific [6]. Therefore, patients diagnosed with dengue require continuous monitoring to prevent symptom worsening and ensure proper

treatment [7].

In smaller cities, the increase in dengue cases is exacerbated by the lack of specialists and advanced medical infrastructure [8, 9]. Basic Health Units (UBS) face challenges in monitoring dengue patients [10]. On the other hand, in larger cities, this scenario results in a high demand for referrals to high-complexity centers without an actual emergency need, due to confusion in the interpretation of the initial symptoms of dengue [8].

Given this context, a remote follow-up application emerges as a viable alternative to optimize care for patients diagnosed with or suspected of having dengue. The objective of this work is to design and implement an initial prototype of such an application, aimed at supporting remote monitoring and indicating whether or not patients require immediate in-person care at healthcare facilities. It is important to emphasize that this article does not present a validated or deployed system. Instead, it introduces the proposal and preliminary implementation of the mobile application, which is still under development and has not yet undergone large-scale testing. Therefore, the work should be understood as a design and implementation proposal rather than a finished.

II. METHODOLOGY

To plan the remote follow-up system, the Design Thinking approach was adopted [11]. This methodology enabled a deeper understanding of both patient and healthcare provider needs. Through questionnaires, data were collected to guide the system's development, aiming to make dengue follow-up more efficient and human-centered. By placing users at the center of the process, we ensured that the final product would be relevant, intuitive, and tailored to their specific demands.

For system development, the SCRUM methodology was used [12], with task management handled via Microsoft Planner. This methodology enabled the system to be built in a flexible and interactive way, allowing easy implementation of adaptations to the project in response to proposed

changes. With SCRUM, development was divided into short, time-boxed sprints during which features were planned, developed, tested, and demonstrated. This flexibility is essential to ensure that the system remains aligned with user needs. Additionally, SCRUM promoted collaboration among team members, transparency, and self-organization, which are crucial for the success of the project.

The implementation phase included selecting an appropriate development platform. Flutter was chosen as the most suitable language for this application [13]. Development was supported by FlutterFlow, a visual tool that allows block-based coding, streamlining collaboration among team members.

The application flow begins with a start screen, where the user selects whether they have a confirmed or suspected dengue diagnosis. If confirmed, they are directed to the login screen; if suspected, they are guided to an initial symptoms checklist. Based on the responses, the system generates an alert recommending login and continued monitoring. After login or registration, the user accesses the home screen, which provides four main pathways: Symptom Tracking, Dengue Information, Healthcare Facilities and Symptom History.

The overall flow of the application is illustrated in Figure 1, providing a visual representation of the user journey from the initial diagnosis selection to the main functionalities. This diagram helps to clarify the sequence of interactions and the logic behind the system's design.

owner through the uid field to ensure data consistency. This entity also includes the timestamp (time_created) and the list of symptoms selected on that day, stored in array format, which allows multiple conditions to be registered simultaneously (e.g., fever, headache, abdominal pain).

III. RESULTS

The implementation of the symptom tracking app focused on alerts for the worsening of clinical conditions based on user input. Upon opening the app, users are prompted to indicate whether they have a confirmed or suspected dengue diagnosis, or proceed without selection (Figure 2). If the user only suspects dengue, they are directed to a mild symptoms checklist (Figure 3), where they assess whether they qualify for more intensive follow-up. Afterward, they are prompted to log in or register (Figure 4a, 4b).

Fig. 1. Application flow diagram showing the sequence of screens and decision points for dengue monitoring

The Firebase database used in this project was structured with two entities: User and Daily_Symptoms. The User entity stores authentication and profile data for each patient, including a unique identifier (uid), e-mail, display name, and account creation time.

The Daily_Symptoms entity records the symptoms reported by each user, with each entry linked to its respective

Fig. 2. Home screen: Confirmed or suspected dengue diagnosis.

Fig. 3. Initial symptom checklist screen.

Fig. 4. (A) Login screen, (B) New user registration screen.

Initial symptoms were based on updated WHO epidemiological data [2], including fever, headache, retro-orbital pain, nausea, rash, and fatigue as part of the

febrile phase, which typically lasts 2–7 days. The app’s logic indicates a low probability of dengue if the symptoms do not include red spots, as these are characteristic of the critical phase, during which hematocrit levels signal worsening symptoms and the need for more intensive monitoring.

The app’s home screen introduces the main functionalities: Symptom Tracking, Dengue Information, Healthcare Facilities, and Symptom History (Figure 5), along with a daily health tip for prevention and care.

Fig. 5. Main menu with symptom tracking, dengue info, service locations, and history.

The severe symptoms page covers both initial and more advanced clinical signs [2]. This feature is the main functionality of the app, as it monitors symptoms that require daily attention through a checklist. An alert is displayed based on the options selected by the user: if no severe symptoms are detected, there is no need for the user to visit medical care centers; if any severe symptom is identified, a warning alert is shown, advising the user to seek medical attention as soon as possible (Figure 6a, 6b). After the alert, the user can choose to save the recorded symptoms or return to the home page, which redirects to the symptom history section.

(A)

(B)

Fig. 6. (A) Alert when no severe symptoms are detected, (B) Alert recommending immediate medical care.

The Symptom History feature provides a timeline with dates, times, and reported symptoms (Figure 7). This allows users to track disease progression and present records during medical consultations if needed.

Fig. 7. Symptom History Screen with the user's recorded daily symptoms

Additional features were implemented to improve access to relevant information, such as care tips, risk factors, prevention strategies, and dietary guidelines (Figure 8). The interface was designed to be user-friendly and accessible, with an emergency contact button, 24/7 technical support, intuitive navigation, and clear icons.

(A)

(B)

Fig. 8. (A) Info screen: News, Nutrition, Alerts, Symptoms; (B) Detailed article access;

IV. DISCUSSION

The results obtained so far consist mainly of the application's prototype screens and the logical flow of symptom tracking. These initial developments highlight the feasibility of building an intuitive and accessible tool for patients with suspected or confirmed dengue. The user-friendly interface and structured symptom classification represent an important step toward digital support for patient monitoring.

Nevertheless, several limitations remain. The application has not yet undergone clinical validation or large-scale testing, which are essential to evaluate its accuracy in detecting severe symptoms and its actual usefulness in public health settings. Additionally, the current prototype does not integrate with official healthcare databases or electronic health records, which limits its applicability in real clinical workflows.

Despite these limitations, the proposed system opens possibilities for future research. Potential improvements include integration with municipal or national health information systems, implementation of real-time alerts for healthcare professionals, and expansion of the system to monitor other arboviruses such as Zika and Chikungunya. These future developments could strengthen the app's role in supporting primary healthcare and optimizing patient follow-up during dengue outbreaks.

V. CONCLUSION

The development of the dengue remote follow-up app prototype using FlutterFlow demonstrates the feasibility of applying low-code platforms to design healthcare-oriented mobile applications. The prototype successfully implemented features such as daily symptom logging, automatic severity alerts, and health information delivery, which can assist patients in monitoring their condition.

At this stage, the results should be interpreted as an initial proof of concept rather than a validated clinical tool. Although the system shows promise, future work will involve clinical validation, large-scale testing, and integration with healthcare services before assessing its actual impact on public health. These steps will be fundamental to determine the app's real contribution to dengue monitoring and patient support.

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